

EFFECTIVE INSTITUTIONAL MECHANISMS FOR THE PREVENTION OF PUBLIC DISORDERS IN FOREIGN STATE PRACTICE

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ANNOTATION

In this article, the legal, organizational, and criminological practices of foreign countries in the field of prevention of public disorders are analyzed. The author examines the public security systems of the United States, the United Kingdom, France, Germany, and the Member States of the European Union, and conducts a comparative analysis of their most effective components. Furthermore, the study explores advanced principles applied in preventive police activities, such as ensuring the protection of human rights, establishing trust-based communication with the public, the effective use of information technologies, and minimizing the use of force. The article identifies the general regularities of foreign experience, including the institutional foundations of prevention, cooperation with the public, and the importance of information analysis and early warning systems. At the same time, the author provides a scientific assessment of the possibilities for adapting foreign models to the context of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The findings of the article possess methodological and practical significance for law enforcement agencies, criminologists, legal scholars, and practitioners.

Key words: public disorder prevention, law enforcement system, comparative legal analysis, public disorder, prevention, public engagement, law enforcement system, preventive activity.

In the modern era, the issue of public security and the prevention of public disorder constitutes one of the priority areas in the activities of law enforcement agencies worldwide. Under the conditions of globalization, socio-political instability, and the growing influence of the Internet and social networks, public disorders can rapidly spread across large territories and pose a serious threat to

societal stability. Therefore, analyzing foreign experience and incorporating it into the improvement of preventive measures within the national system is of paramount importance.

In the United States, the prevention and management of public disorder are based on clearly defined legal and tactical frameworks at both the federal and local levels. The Public Order Management system is regarded as a key component of police activity. Within this framework, primary emphasis is placed on community cooperation, preventive policing, and the minimization of the use of force.

According to the "Crowd Management and Control" programs developed by the U.S. Federal Counterterrorism Agency and city police departments, a special risk analysis is conducted before each major public event, and an action plan is developed in collaboration with community organizations. Police officers also receive specialized training in de-escalation techniques. Body cameras, accountability reports, and open communication with citizens have become important elements of crowd prevention [1].

In the UK, the public order policing system is traditionally based on the principles of protecting rights and freedoms, fostering dialogue with the public, and the lawful use of force. In this country, the command and control system plays a key role in managing public disorder. Every police department has a "Public Order Unit" specifically trained to handle public events. All police actions are carried out in accordance with the Police and Criminal Evidence Act 1984 and the Public Order Act 1986. When working with the public, a "negotiation management" approach is used. This method involves establishing an ongoing dialogue with the organizers of public demonstrations, which reduces the likelihood of unrest [2].

In France, public order maintenance (POL) has historically been a key element of state security. This system is primarily implemented by two agencies: the National

Police and the Gendarmerie. They each have specialized tactical programs used to maintain public order.

In French practice, the concept of "prevention of public disorder" (prevention of public disorder) plays a key role. This system emphasizes operational intelligence gathering, monitoring social media activity, and engaging with the public. The use of force by the police in France is strictly limited by law [3].

In Germany, prevention of mass unrest is based on advances in psychology and sociology, as well as legal frameworks. The method of monitoring and accompanying demonstrations (Demobegleitung) plays a key role in the peaceful conduct of mass events. Police officers are trained to establish dialogue with demonstrators, defuse the situation, and use force only when necessary. The Bundeswehr and state police undergo specialized training programs on "Crowd Psychology." Local authorities and public organizations actively participate in preventive measures. In the German experience, the principle of "social partnership"—that is, the development of a system of trusting relationships between the public and government authorities—is of great importance [4].

At the European Union level, a number of joint programs are being implemented to prevent public disorder. For example, the European Police College (CEPOL) organizes regular training courses on "Public Order and Crowd Management." Europol also facilitates the exchange of information on preventing situations leading to public disorder [5].

In the Netherlands, Sweden, and Norway, "early warning systems" are widely used. These systems identify dangerous phone calls and social media activity in advance and report them to law enforcement.

Experience from other countries shows that the use of force alone is ineffective in preventing mass unrest. The focus should be on prevention, building trust with the public, and using psychological and informational tools. Furthermore,

police training, public relations skills, and an accountability system will yield effective results if refined.

A key lesson for Uzbekistan is the integration of international models by adapting them to the national legal system and cultural environment. This will not only ensure public safety but also guarantee the rights and freedoms of citizens.

Violence, mass killings, and riots at sporting events pose a serious danger to society. This danger extends beyond sports facilities and surrounding areas and extends beyond sport and public relations. Sports law theory and the school of law are actively developing to strengthen their practical applications, including addressing the most pressing security challenges of sporting events. In this regard, it is important to expand the scientific community of sports law specialists with "clean forces" who will help address the most important and complex challenges of law enforcement in this social sphere.

Unfortunately, many important foreign sources on sports, particularly those published in French, Spanish, Italian, and Portuguese, remain unknown to the general public of researchers and practitioners in our country.

When developing legislation for the Republic of Uzbekistan on law enforcement in the field of sports, it is necessary to draw on similar international experience in legal regulation.

Various countries, relying on national sports legislation, create conditions for the development of physical culture and sports in their countries, depending on their political and socioeconomic systems. This primarily involves ensuring law and order by combining the efforts of the state, its governmental, public, and private organizations, institutions, and organizations. European countries have long been addressing this issue. Legislative changes have been made at the national level, and international documents on this issue have been adopted. The dramatic events that led to the deaths of 38 people at the stadium in Heysel, Belgium, in May 1985

prompted the Council of Europe to develop the first European Convention on Spectator Violence and Violent Behavior. This international legal instrument, which entered into force on November 1 of that year, has become one of the foundations for combating such incidents on the continent. Specifically, when it comes to football matches, the Convention obliges states to take specific measures to prevent violence during sporting events in general, providing for criminal prosecution and punishment.

The French Sports Code (Code du sport) is of great interest for the following reasons:

- this legal act, for the first time and (so far) uniquely, systematizes the key issues of ensuring safety at sporting events (albeit briefly, but very substantively);
- the French experience in this regard could be very useful for the development and regulation of physical culture and sports, as the local legal system belongs to the Romano-Germanic legal family, which creates additional opportunities for incorporating the positive foreign experience of these countries both in local lawmaking and in law enforcement (primarily law enforcement) [6].

In general, the French Sports Code does not create new rules, but merely consolidates existing law. The provisions of documents not included in the Code lose their legal force. This Code consists of a total of 1,675 articles. Based on the specific features of the French legal system, the French Sports Code includes both legislative and regulatory acts. According to the French Sports Code, being intoxicated at a sports venue during a sporting event or public broadcast is punishable by a fine of €7,500. If the perpetrator is found guilty of committing violent acts resulting in total incapacity for less than a week, they are punishable by imprisonment for one year and a fine of \$2,000. Entering or attempting to enter a sports facility while intoxicated, by force, or by deception during a sporting event or public broadcast is punishable by imprisonment for one year and a fine of €15,000.

Unauthorized entry into public sporting events, as well as the use of explosive devices or any objects that could be used as a weapon, is prohibited. According to Article 132-75 of the French Penal Code, unauthorized entry into a sports facility during a sporting event or public broadcast of an explosive device, pyrotechnic device, or any object that could be used as a weapon is punishable by imprisonment for up to three years and a fine of €15,000. Similar penalties are provided for attempting to commit the crime specified in the first paragraph.

Despite the rapid digitalization of social relations, mass unrest, as a form of collective expression of public discontent, remains one of the most pressing and complex social problems affecting individual states and the international community as a whole. In the context of globalization and the continuous development of information technology, the factors contributing to the emergence of such destructive phenomena are becoming increasingly diverse and interconnected.

Within a single region, mass unrest can indicate systemic crises that require immediate attention not only from law enforcement agencies but also from other agencies involved in ensuring the peace of citizens. Examples of such situations can be observed in various countries, where discontent escalates into actual criminal acts, threatening the integrity of society and undermining trust in government officials. In such circumstances, it is especially important to understand the mechanisms underlying such actions and develop strategies for their prevention and management.

In the international arena, mass unrest is becoming a focus for law enforcement agencies, research institutes, and states seeking to analyze and prevent conflicts that could have cross-border consequences. The collaboration of various global community actors, as well as international efforts to monitor and assess such conflict situations, highlight the need for a comprehensive approach to studying this problem.

Modern research in this area emphasizes the need for a comprehensive understanding of delinquent behavior as a highly harmful crime, which requires studying the causes, forms, and methods of combating such manifestations, taking into account not only national but also international experience.

In international literature, this destructive phenomenon is viewed as a systemic phenomenon affecting the entire range of spheres of activity that ensure the normal functioning of social relations. Experts note that mass unrest not only threatens the immediate physical safety of citizens but also leads to significant economic losses and disrupts the functioning of social institutions, which is particularly noticeable in countries with weak public administration structures. Furthermore, they emphasize the advisability of considering social factors in the security policies and measures implemented by government agencies [7].

The psychological approach studies mass riots in direct relation to the phenomenon of crowds, that is, the types of crowds that commit riots, their motives, their psychology, methods and means of influencing participants' consciousness, changes in crowd behavior, and the processes associated with crowd management. According to the psychological approach, a crowd is a group of people that is not separately organized, spontaneously formed, chaotic, lacking a common goal, and subject to pure emotions [8].

When studying mass unrest, its causes, and consequences, a systematic approach is necessary, taking into account the diversity of factors that determine this phenomenon.

With this in mind, this study utilized the following mechanism (algorithm) for scientifically substantiating the social danger of the illegal phenomenon of interest: examining the socio-legal significance of the protest movement; studying the specifics of the legal assessment of this criminal activity not only through the prism

of domestic but also foreign legislation; and examining the grounds for its criminalization from the perspective of the fundamental characteristics of the crime.

The social danger factor is the key element distinguishing a criminal offense from other forms of deviant behavior. In humanitarian doctrine, this is traditionally associated with the risk of harm to protected legal relations or the imminent occurrence of such harm. This, in turn, must demonstrate an objective and justified need to impose the remedies provided for by the Criminal Code. In this regard, special attention should be paid to the principle of fairness, which requires proportionate consideration of not only the immediate but also the long-term consequences of these events for social and political stability. In this regard, the application of relevant sectoral legislation is determined by a combination of the following conditions:

1. High level of harm. The event in question constitutes an uncontrollable threat to public order and public safety. In international practice, such events often result in significant material losses, violation of citizens' rights, and the disruption of infrastructure. Its conceptual characteristics include the presence of multiple objects of criminal law protection (public order and security, life, health, physical integrity of the individual, property, governance, and state power), a violent method of committing the act, and an intentional form of guilt. It should be noted that legal doctrine lacks a unified view regarding the direct object of this crime. Furthermore, the validity of this view is confirmed by the results of the survey conducted as part of this study.

2. Radicalization of the population. This form of criminal activity creates favorable conditions for extremist sentiments. This connection is explained by a number of factors, including increased social tension, polarization of views, and the development of a sense of injustice, especially in the context of state suppression of protests using violent measures. The similarity of these phenomena lies in the very

nature of their origins, as the term "extremism" itself was initially used to describe political and social movements seeking fundamental changes in society. Subsequently, the specific means and methods used to achieve this goal elevated this activity to the level of an unconditional threat, including to national security. A certain degree of uniformity in the forms of criminal behavior under consideration is also observed in the legislative sphere, including in the legal sphere of foreign countries. Article 1 of the Law of the Republic of Belarus of January 4, 2007, No. 203-Z "On Combating Extremism" is confirmed by the survey results, according to which 77% of respondents supported the position expressed in this context.

3. The need for adequate legal protection of legally protected interests. Mass riots accompanied by violence and vandalism, posing a threat to life and health, cause harm significantly exceeding the consequences of administrative offenses or other illegal actions. In such circumstances, criminal law protection acts not only as a means of retribution but also as a guarantee of the security of all legally protected interests – from the personal integrity of citizens to the safety of public and state property.

4. Preventive action. Mass riots tend to spread rapidly and can attract an increasing number of participants, increasing the level of violence and destruction. Criminal penalties for participation in this illegal activity help reduce escalation by preventing the "spread of contagion" effect, whereby initial participants attract ever-increasing numbers of people. Strict sanctions help establish clear boundaries of acceptable behavior and prevent global involvement in the conflict, facilitating the localization of incidents and reducing their scale.

5. Systemic nature of the threat. This criminal activity often has complex consequences that extend across various spheres of public life, causing significant damage to urban infrastructure, transportation networks, and other vital infrastructure for local populations. For example, when riots are accompanied by

attacks on hospitals or schools, this creates an additional threat to the lives of citizens, especially vulnerable groups such as children, the elderly, and the sick. The disruption of public institutions not only deprives citizens of essential services but also increases social tension. Criminal law has the means to respond to systemic threats, encompassing all aspects of damage.

The development of a public and legal consciousness and legal culture based on rejection of any manifestations of radicalism, the improvement of interagency cooperation among law enforcement agencies, and the promotion of positive moral guidelines and adherence to ethical standards are of paramount importance in combating this destructive phenomenon.

In this context, criminalization plays a key role as one of the main areas of criminal policy, including through the creation of a qualified framework for regulating acts committed via the internet, as well as another key framework for crimes related to the financing of mass unrest. These measures are aimed at modernizing law enforcement mechanisms, taking into account contemporary social and legal realities, as well as the actual state and level of development of the relevant category of crimes in the country.

The forensic approach to preventing mass riots is based on a thorough study of the root causes, mechanisms, and methods of leaving traces of crime. This allows for preventive measures to be implemented not only after the crime has been committed, but also during its prevention.

Thus, the forensic study of mass riots is an important scientific and practical approach to ensuring peace, stability, and law and order in society.

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